

The Spatiotemporal Variations of Total Column Ozone Concentration over Ethiopia

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We have studied the spatiotemporal characteristics of ozone concentration over Ethiopia using data from Ozone Mapper and Profiling Suite OMPS Nadir Mapper (OMPS- NM). Daily total column ozone data of 108 observation points with spatial resolution $1^\circ \times 1^\circ$ over the study area for the period 2012 – 2019 have been analyzed. The spatial variations over the region have been studied by considering the longitudinal and latitudinal bands separately through the sample mean difference among different bands using multicomparison analysis of variance technique in order to identify the clusters in the region. For the temporal variability, we model the total column ozone time series observation as a sum of seasonal, trend and temporally correlated noise components. We have found that the total column ozone concentration has a maximum value of 301DU during summer on August 18, 2013 and a minimum value of 216DU during winter on January 03, 2013 over the study period. The 95% confidence level of the overall mean of total column ozone concentration during the study period was found to be (261.35 ± 2.38) DU. Our spatial data analysis revealed that the spatial distribution of ozone over Ethiopia can be classified into three clusters: Southern Cluster ($4.5^\circ N - 8.5^\circ N$ & $33.5^\circ E - 47.5^\circ E$), North-Eastern Cluster ($9.5^\circ N$ to $14.5^\circ N$ & $41.5^\circ E - 47.5^\circ E$) and North-Western Cluster ($9.5^\circ N - 14.5^\circ N$ & $33.5^\circ E - 40.5^\circ E$). We have checked the coefficient of determination among bands in same cluster to see if the concentration of ozone in one band can be explained by the concentration in another band for each cluster and confirmed the reliability of the classification. In order to capture the temporal characteristics, we have computed the spectral periodogram for each cluster and obtained a power peak at frequency $f = 0.002768Hz$, which indicates that the ozone concentration over the region exhibits an annual cyclic behavior. A truncated Fourier series fit is used to determine the annual seasonal component. The non-parametric Mann-Kendall's trend test with a 95% confidence level of significant has indicated a decreasing linear trend with a depletion rate of 0.77 DU/yr, 0.73 DU/yr, and 0.43 DU/yr over North-Western, North-Eastern & Southern clusters respectively. The analysis of residuals for each cluster indicated that the residuals are normally distributed with no significant outliers and the model explains 85%, 86% and 79% of the variance in the North-West, North-East and Southern clusters respectively, demonstrating the reliability of the model considered in this study.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ozone is a chemically active colorless gas that reacts with many other substances. It plays a vital role in controlling the chemical composition and climate of the atmosphere¹⁻³. Ozone can be considered as harmful or good depending on its function. The function of ozone varies depending on its location in the atmosphere and its level of concentration. It is found primarily in two regions of the atmosphere. About 10 % of atmospheric ozone is found in the troposphere, the region from the surface of the earth up to $\approx 10km$ altitude, while the remaining 90 % is found in the stratosphere, the region between the top of the troposphere till about 50 km altitude. Stratospheric ozone is useful in absorbing the dangerous ultraviolet radiation from the sun and protects living things below it. Near the Earth's surface, the ozone's reactive nature can damage ecosystems when it is beyond the natural background level. For example, it can cause rubbers to crack, hurt plants and result in respiratory diseases in humans. It is important to study and characterize the concentration of ozone and its corresponding dynamics both at regional and global levels. Total Column Ozone (TCO) at any location is found by measuring all the ozone in the atmosphere directly above that loca-

tion using ground-based stations and satellites. The total column ozone (TCO) is the total amount of atmospheric ozone up to the height of the stratopause and is measured as an integrated values of ozone over the column of unit cross-section. The TCO concentration amounting to less than 220 DU are usually considered as an indicator of ozone hole formation in the polar regions⁴⁻⁶. The ozone hole has gained worldwide attention and this is due to its association with harmful effects of UV rays including cancer risks and effects on plants and animals. Over exposure to ultraviolet radiation from the sun is one of the major reasons for skin cancer⁷⁻⁹. The study of the variability of ozone concentration using measurements and models has become a major topic of research around world¹⁰⁻¹³. The spatiotemporal dynamics of TCO at both regional and global levels has attracted the attention of many researchers. For example,^{10,14} have shown a decreasing trend in TCO concentration in the middle and high latitudes of both hemispheres during the late 1970s to the mid 1990s.⁴ also have shown that the levels of ozone near the equatorial regions are lower than the global average value. Although the global mean ozone distribution of TCO is largely controlled by the large-scale stratospheric circulation, there is a large degree of year to year and shorter-term variability in tropical TCO¹⁵. Studying the variations of ozone concentration over

a specific region plays an important role in understanding the environmental conditions including estimating the level of exposure to ultraviolet radiation.

Rafiq et. al.¹ analysed the seasonal and inter-annual variations of TCO over Pakistan region from AQUA-AIRS Level-3 Daily Global satellite data during 2003–2011. They used simple averages to determine the monthly, inter-annual and annual TCO variations. Their study has indicated that in Northern Pakistan region, $30^{\circ}N - 37^{\circ}N$, the maximum ozone concentration occurs in winter (DJF) season and the minimum in summer (JJA). Whereas, in southern part of Pakistan, ($23^{\circ}N - 29^{\circ}N$), they have shown that the highest ozone level was recorded in the summer while the lowest record was in the winter season.¹⁶ also investigated the spatiotemporal variability of TCO over the Yangtze River Delta, the most populated region in China, using TCO data from the Total Ozone Mapping Spectrometer (TOMS) for the period 1978–2005 and from Ozone Monitoring Instrument (OMI) for the period 2004–2013. They computed coefficient of relative variation for each latitudinal and longitudinal band to quantify the spatial variability and modelled the seasonality as an annual cycle with a sinusoidal function. This study does not contain information on why the authors consider annual cycle in the seasonality in order to justify the reason for fitting the data with an annual periodic sinusoidal function. In such a study, determining a correct seasonal behaviour is crucial as the seasonality might also affect the trend analysis result. In our study we investigate the spectral periodogram of TCO time series to determine the power peak and the corresponding frequencies in order to identify seasonalities from time series data correctly. In this paper, we are interested to study the spatiotemporal characteristics of TCO over Ethiopia using daily ozone concentration data from OMPS- NM. The objectives of this study can be considered as twofold. The first objective is to capture the spatial variability of ozone concentration over Ethiopia and study the spatial patterns if there is any clustering of regions using the overall TCO mean along latitude and longitude through difference of sample mean tests and multiple group comparison tests. The second objective is to understand the temporal variations using time series analysis of TCO of each cluster. The analysis is carried out by resolving the TCO time series into seasonal, trend and temporally correlated residual components. In order to optimize model performance and to capture regular, but non-constant variance changes between different seasons, we incorporate temporal correlations and seasonal variances in the model. This kind of regional study on spatiotemporal variations of TCO can provide valuable insights on regional drivers of TCO concentration for many environmental and health related policy discussions. Since more ultraviolet radiation reaches over Ethiopian regions as compared to high latitudes¹⁷, continuous monitoring of the variability of TCO concentration is important. Moreover, ozone concentrations over the tropics is highly linked with the tropical atmosphere dynamics. This means that characteristics of TCO distribution over different regions of Ethiopia provide valuable insight about the underlying atmospheric dynamics.

II. THE DATA AND ANALYSIS METHOD

A. Study Area

Ethiopia is located in the North-Eastern part of Africa, which lies approximately between $3^{\circ}N$ & $15^{\circ}N$ latitude and $33^{\circ}E$ & $48^{\circ}E$ longitude. There are four seasons in Ethiopia including winter (DJF), spring (MAM), summer (JJA) and autumn (SON). The topography of Ethiopia is highly diverse, with an elevation ranging around 125 m below sea level in the Danakil depression to 4620 m above sea level for Ras Dashaen mountain range. The climate varies with altitude, from the arid climate of the lowest altitudes to the cool climate of the plateau. Understanding the spatiotemporal dynamics of ozone concentration over such a diverse topography and climate can provide critical information for environmental policy formulation and discussion.

In this study, we have used data from OMPS- NM sampled at 108 observation points from the study area as indicated in Fig. 1. The OMPS- NM was built by Ball Aerospace & Technologies Corporation for measuring the concentration of ozone in the Earth's atmosphere¹⁸.

We have used the Version 2.1 OMPS-NM gridded data, obtained from NASA Goddard Space Flight Center Website for a period ranging 2012 - 2019 with $1^{\circ} \times 1^{\circ}$ resolution¹⁹. Takele²⁰, 2013 and Chen²¹, 2013 have validated the OMI and OMPS data sets respectively for the study area. We have used bi-linear interpolation in order to obtain estimates for the missing data points in the temporal analysis as suggested by²².

FIG. 1: Data points of OMPS-NM satellite over Ethiopia, it has 15 columns and 12 rows as longitudinal and latitudinal bands respectively.

B. Analysis Method

The characteristics of TCO distribution over Ethiopia are investigated by classifying the region into sub-regions or clusters based on the levels of TCO concentrations and by carrying out timeseries analysis of TCO for each cluster. We have classified the study area into representative sub-regions using spatial data clustering technique. We used difference of sample mean tests of analysis of variance followed by multiple group comparison tests for the spatial clustering. The analysis has been carried out by using fifteen longitudinal and twelve latitudinal bands data over the region by considering measurement values along same longitude as a longitudinal band and data values along same latitude as a latitudinal band, respectively. In order to study the longitudinal integrated temporal variations of ozone as a function of a latitude band, we denote the ozone measurements for the i^{th} latitudinal band at time t by $C_{t,i}$. We can then express the latitudinal and temporal varying measurement matrix C_{lat} by

$$C_{\text{lat}} = (C_{t,i})_{2890 \times 12} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{1,1} & C_{1,2} & \dots & C_{1,12} \\ C_{2,1} & C_{2,2} & \dots & C_{2,12} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ C_{2890,1} & C_{2890,2} & \dots & C_{2890,12} \end{pmatrix} \quad (1)$$

where $C_{t,i}$ is the longitudinal integrated TCO measurement over the i^{th} latitudinal band at time t , and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 12$ denotes the latitudinal bands that corresponds with $3.5^\circ, 4.5^\circ, \dots, 14.5^\circ$ North and $t = 1, 2, \dots, 2890$ represents time, which is the days of the year in the study period from February 2012 to December 2019.

Similarly, to study longitudinal variations of ozone, we use the longitudinal and temporal varying measurement matrix, denoted as C_{lon} , and it is given by

$$C_{\text{lon}} = (C_{t,j})_{2890 \times 15} = \begin{pmatrix} C_{1,1} & C_{1,2} & \dots & C_{1,15} \\ C_{2,1} & C_{2,2} & \dots & C_{2,15} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \dots & \vdots \\ C_{2890,1} & C_{2890,2} & \dots & C_{2890,15} \end{pmatrix} \quad (2)$$

where $C_{t,j}$ is the latitudinal integrated TCO measurement over the j^{th} longitudinal band at time t , and $i = 1, 2, \dots, 15$ denotes the longitudinal bands that corresponds with $33.5^\circ, 34.5^\circ, \dots, 47.5^\circ$ East and $t = 1, 2, \dots, 2890$ represents time, which is the days of the year in the study period from February 2012 to December 2019.

We can now classify the TCO distribution over Ethiopia into sub-regions by assessing the existence of difference between the sample means. This is carried out by using the analysis variance technique^{23,24}, which can be described by

$$F = \left(\frac{\sum_j n_j (\bar{C}_j - \bar{C})^2}{\sum_j \sum_t (C_{t,j} - \bar{C}_j)^2} \right) \left(\frac{N - k}{k - 1} \right), \quad (3)$$

where n_j , $C_{t,j}$, N , \bar{C} , \bar{C}_j , k , and F refers the number of observations on j^{th} band, values of integrated TCO value for

j^{th} band at time t , total number of observations over all bands, overall mean of TCO, mean of TCO for j^{th} band, total number of bands and variation between sample means respectively. By comparing F values with the critical value of the F distribution at 95% confidence level, we can classify the observation points based on the result of analysis of variance into a particular cluster. The analysis of variance method tells us whether there is a difference of sample mean or not between the clusters. However, it doesn't tell us whether the concentration of total column ozone in one cluster can be explained by the concentration in another cluster. For the coefficient of determination of ozone concentration among clusters, we use the coefficient of determination directly, which can be expressed by

$$R_{j,k}^2 = \frac{(\sum_j C_j C_k - N \bar{C}_j \bar{C}_k)^2}{(\sum_j C_j^2 - N \bar{C}_j^2) (\sum_k C_k^2 - N \bar{C}_k^2)}, \quad (4)$$

where $N, C_j, C_k, \bar{C}_j, \bar{C}_k$, and $R_{j,k}^2$ refers the number of data pairs, values of integrated TCO value for j^{th} band, values of integrated TCO value for k^{th} band, mean of TCO for j^{th} band, mean of TCO for k^{th} band and the coefficient of determination between j^{th} and k^{th} bands respectively.

C. Clustering Performance

Clustering validation has been recognized as one of the vital issues essential to the success of clustering applications. In this article, we focus on the internal clustering validation, as there are no ground data.

The Calinski-Harabasz index also known as the Variance Ratio Criterion, is the ratio of the sum of between-clusters dispersion and of inter-cluster dispersion for all clusters, the higher the score, the more distinct the clusters. The Calinski-Harabasz index is defined as

$$VRC_k = \frac{SS_B(N - K)}{SS_W(K - 1)}, \quad (5)$$

where, SS_B is the overall between-cluster variance, SS_W is the overall within-cluster variance, k is the number of clusters, and N is the number of observations.

The overall between-cluster variance SS_B is defined as

$$SS_B = \sum_{i=1}^k n_i \|m_i - m\|^2, \quad (6)$$

where, k is the number of clusters, n_i is the number of observations in cluster i , m_i is the centroid of cluster i , m is the overall mean of the sample data, and $\|m_i - m\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the two vectors.

The overall within-cluster variance SS_W is defined as

$$SS_W = \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{x_i \in C_i} \|x - m_i\|^2, \quad (7)$$

where, k is the number of clusters, x is a data point, c_i is the i th cluster, m_i is the centroid of cluster i , and $\|x - m_i\|$ is the Euclidean distance between the two vectors.

D. Timeseries Analysis

Timeseries analysis for all the clusters was carried out independently from the mean values of all the observations in that particular cluster for each day of the year. Here, we decomposed the daily timeseries data from each cluster into seasonal, trend and residual components. We didn't consider other cyclic component in our definition as we are working with a short period of data (only eight years data). Hence, we defined the timeseries with additive components as:

$$Y_t = S_t + T_t + \varepsilon_t, \quad (8)$$

where S_t , T_t and ε_t are the Seasonal or Cyclic variation, trend component and residual components, respectively of the mean value data Y_t corresponding to each cluster.

The cyclic fluctuation of the timeseries is determined as the best fit of the daily measured TCO timeseries data^{25,26}. The seasonality or cyclic fluctuation component of TCO timeseries is usually modeled with a one term Fourier series model^{16,27}. The main challenge here is determining the period of the cycle. We used power spectrum Fast Fourier transform (FFT) on the de-trended data to identify the dominant frequency. In our case, we get only one dominant frequency which accounts with the annual periodicity of the seasonality in the TCO series. We defined the cyclic component of the TCO as

$$S_t = \alpha_0 + \sum_{i=1}^n \alpha_i \cdot \sin(i \cdot \omega t) + \sum_{i=1}^n \beta_i \cdot \cos(i \cdot \omega t), \quad (9)$$

where t refers the time in days of year, α_i and β_i are free parameters to be determined from the data and $\omega = 2\pi f$, where f is the dominant frequency from FFT.

Before defining the trend, we would like to check its existence and behavior through non-parametric Mann Kendall test. The Mann-Kendall test can capture a highly significant trend²⁸. The main advantage of this method is that it is not sensitive to outliers and the data do not need to conform to any particular distribution. The Mann-Kendall test is described mathematically as

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{j=i+1}^n \text{sgn}(X_j - X_i), \quad (10)$$

for

$$\text{sgn}(X_j - X_i) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } X_j - X_i > 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } X_j - X_i = 0, 1 \leq i < j \leq n, \\ -1 & \text{if } X_j - X_i < 0 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where X_j and X_i refer to TCO concentration at the j^{th} and i^{th} time respectively. The corresponding variance is

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{1}{18} (n(n-1)(2n+5) - \sum_{j=1}^p t_j(t_j-1)(2t_j+5)), \quad (12)$$

where p refers to the number of values with more than one occurrence (tied groups) in X , and t_j is the number of occurrences of the multiple value in the j^{th} tied group.

Then, the standardized test statistic Z is computed by

$$Z = \begin{cases} \frac{S-1}{\sigma} & \text{if } S > 0, \\ 0 & \text{if } S = 0, \\ \frac{S+1}{\sigma} & \text{if } S < 0 \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

The presence of a statistically significant trend is evaluated from the Z value and the null hypothesis is rejected if the absolute value of Z is larger than the theoretical value $Z_{1-\alpha}$, where $\alpha = 0.05$ is considered as the statistical significance level. The long term increasing or decreasing pattern of TCO timeseries have been modeled using linear trend in Africa²⁹. In this study, we also considered a linear trend for the eight years data, defined as

$$T_t = \gamma t + \alpha_0, \quad (14)$$

where γ and α_0 are the slope and intercept of the trend line to be determined from the data respectively.

To describe the serial correlation in the data and non-constant variance, we model the error term ε_t as a blocked AR(3) process, with periodic boundary conditions within each block

$$\varepsilon_{sn+k}^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^3 \phi_i^{(k)} \varepsilon_{sn+k-i}^{(k)} + v_{sn+k}, \quad (15)$$

where $k = 1, 2, \dots, n$ is period index, $s = 0, 1, \dots, m-1$ is year index and v_{sn+k} is noise term with $E(v_{sn+k}) = 0$ and $\text{Var}(v_{sn+k}) = \sigma_v^2(k)$. The idea of modeling the serial correlated residual as in equation (15) is similar to Cochrane–Orcutt correction in classical multiple regression^{30,31}. Then using regression technique to estimate v_{sn+k} for the regression parameters ϕ_1, ϕ_2 and ϕ_3 , we can write Equation (15) in compact form as $\vec{\varepsilon} = \mathbf{E}\vec{\phi} + \vec{v}$. Then the parameters can be estimated as

$$\hat{\vec{\phi}} = (\mathbf{E}^T \Gamma^{-1} \mathbf{E})^{-1} \mathbf{E}^T \Gamma^{-1} \vec{\varepsilon},$$

where $\Gamma = \text{diag}(\vec{\mathbf{I}}_m \otimes \vec{\sigma}_v^2)$ is covariance matrix of the noise term \vec{v} with σ_v obtained from Equation (18) and $\vec{\mathbf{I}}_m$, a vector of ones of length m . An estimate of the noise term v_{sn+k} can be computed by

$$\hat{v} = \vec{\varepsilon} - \mathbf{E}\hat{\vec{\phi}}.$$

Then, the standard deviation of the noise term v_{sn+k} is obtained as

$$\sigma_v(k) = \sqrt{\frac{1}{m} \sum_{s=0}^{m-1} v_{sn+k}^2}. \quad (16)$$

The blocked AR(3) model used to represent the noise term $\vec{\epsilon}$ can also be rewritten in matrix form as:

$$\mathbf{L}\vec{\epsilon} = \vec{v}, \quad (17)$$

where the coefficient matrix $\mathbf{L} = \mathbf{I}_m \otimes \mathbf{J}$ for an $n \times n$ matrix \mathbf{J} given by

$$\mathbf{J} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 \\ -\phi_1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 \\ -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\phi_3 \\ -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 & 1 & \dots & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ & & & & \ddots & & & & \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \dots & -\phi_3 & -\phi_2 & -\phi_1 & 1 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The relation obtained in Equation (17) is useful to ease computation of the inverse covariance matrix of the measurement noise during model uncertainty quantification.

Non-constant Variance

In order to ensure that the model parameter uncertainty is as correct as possible, we include the seasonally varying variance in the error term $\vec{\epsilon}$ by approximating the standard deviation of the noise term v_{sn+k} by the trigonometric polynomial

$$\hat{\sigma}_v(k) = a_0 + \sum_{i=1}^3 \{a_i \cos(2\pi ik/n) + b_i \sin(2\pi ik/n)\}, \quad (18)$$

where a_0 , a_i and b_i are unrestricted parameters to be estimated by fitting the trigonometric polynomial to the model in (16), so that this polynomial is strictly positive.

Here, the reason to consider serial correlated noise and non-constant variance in the model is motivated as would be expected from the QBO, solar cycle, and other interannual variability in the ozone time series.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A. Spatial Variations of TCO

1. Latitudinal TCO Variations

We have studied the latitudinal variations of TCO by calculating the daily difference of TCO value between the northernmost region of Ethiopia ($14.5^\circ N$) and the values at the other eleven latitude bands sequentially. We used the coefficient of determination parameter (R^2) using Equation (4). These yield the standard deviations and the coefficient of determination parameter values for latitudinal band differences as in Table I.

The tabular values indicate that the statistical differences between the value of TCO at the northernmost latitude of Ethiopia and its value at other lower latitude bands increase as the distance of separation increases. The coefficient of determination parameter (R^2) between TCO value at the northernmost latitude and other bands demonstrates similar results.

TABLE I: Statistical parameters that depict the difference between the mean daily TCO value at northern most latitude ($14.5^\circ N$) and other latitudinal bands over Ethiopia

Latitude	Std	$ \mu_1 - \mu_2 $	R^2
$14.5^\circ N - 13.5^\circ N$	1.6	0.5	0.989
$14.5^\circ N - 12.5^\circ N$	2.7	1.57	0.969
$14.5^\circ N - 11.5^\circ N$	3.74	3.29	0.942
$14.5^\circ N - 10.5^\circ N$	4.75	3.56	0.907
$14.5^\circ N - 9.5^\circ N$	5.75	3.71	0.864
$14.5^\circ N - 8.5^\circ N$	6.77	3.5	0.809
$14.5^\circ N - 7.5^\circ N$	7.78	3.0	0.742
$14.5^\circ N - 6.5^\circ N$	8.74	2.73	0.668
$14.5^\circ N - 5.5^\circ N$	9.58	1.86	0.596
$14.5^\circ N - 4.5^\circ N$	10.39	1.8	0.526
$14.5^\circ N - 3.5^\circ N$	11.14	0.86	0.461

We can see that the values of the coefficient of determination measure the strength of the relationship between TCO characteristics at the northernmost latitude region and other latitudinal bands.

An R^2 value > 0.8 means that at least 80% of the variance in the northernmost ($14.5^\circ N$) band can be explained by the variance in the compared band. Choosing 80% as a criterion for statistical representativeness³², the observations at ($14.5^\circ N$) can be described by variations in latitude bands down to 8.5° indicating similarities in TCO values over 6° latitude coverage.

2. Longitudinal TCO Variation

Similarly, the longitudinal variations of TCO have been investigated by evaluating the statistical difference between the mean daily value of TCO observed over the most Eastern tip of Ethiopia ($47.5^\circ E$) and TCO values over other lower longitudinal regions. Table II shows the standard deviations, mean difference and the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the respective bands.

Table II shows that for most longitudes, values of R^2 are greater than 0.8 with the lowest value of 0.777. This means that at least 77% of the variability in the observation at 47.5° can be represented from TCO observations up to 33.5° . In order to map out regions with similar TCO values in more details, we have used spatial clustering technique.

B. Clustering TCO measurements over Ethiopia

It is practical to classify all data points into representative sub-regions and investigate the distribution of TCO measurements at different topographical and climate zones of Ethiopia. We carried out the clustering of TCO values for the study area using Equation (3). We give discussion for the longitudinal and latitudinal clusters in detail in the subsequent subsections.

TABLE II: Statistical parameters that depict the difference between TCO daily mean value at $47.5^{\circ}E$ and its value at other lower longitudinal bands.

Longitude	Std	$ \mu_1 - \mu_2 $	R^2
$47.5^{\circ}E - 46.5^{\circ}E$	2.91	1.01	0.946
$47.5^{\circ}E - 45.5^{\circ}E$	2.21	0.45	0.969
$47.5^{\circ}E - 44.5^{\circ}E$	3.47	1.80	0.924
$47.5^{\circ}E - 43.5^{\circ}E$	3.11	1.49	0.939
$47.5^{\circ}E - 42.5^{\circ}E$	4.09	1.85	0.895
$47.5^{\circ}E - 41.5^{\circ}E$	4.2	0.54	0.893
$47.5^{\circ}E - 40.5^{\circ}E$	4.73	5.48	0.863
$47.5^{\circ}E - 39.5^{\circ}E$	4.59	1.98	0.871
$47.5^{\circ}E - 38.5^{\circ}E$	4.83	5.2	0.854
$47.5^{\circ}E - 37.5^{\circ}E$	4.88	6.26	0.855
$47.5^{\circ}E - 36.5^{\circ}E$	5.27	2.83	0.825
$47.5^{\circ}E - 35.5^{\circ}E$	5.1	5.18	0.836
$47.5^{\circ}E - 34.5^{\circ}E$	5.95	1.08	0.777
$47.5^{\circ}E - 33.5^{\circ}E$	5.87	2.67	0.783

1. Longitudinal Clustering

We used the null hypothesis to classify the TCO corresponding to a specific longitudinal band. We defined the null hypothesis here as follows.

- H_0 : There is no mean difference between any two longitudinal bands,
- H_1 : There is mean difference at least between two of the longitudinal bands.

We test for differences in the longitudinal sample means by computing the F value from Equation (3) and comparing it against the distribution of F values valid for the null hypothesis, which is defined as no longitudinal band sample mean is significantly different than any other longitudinal band sample mean. If the computed F-value is more extreme than 95% of the null hypothesis distribution (p-value < 0.05) we reject the null hypothesis. If the null hypothesis is rejected, we then carry out a multiple comparison technique to identify which longitudinal sample means are different and which are similar to define the clusters. Table (III) shows the individual terms from Equation (3) and the resulting F-value and p-value. The p-value is less than 0.05 so we reject the null hypothesis. In Table (III), the total degree of freedom is 40614 due to the missing data values in C_{lon} (Eqn.2) that can't be replaced with the linear interpolation. Table (IV) shows the results from the multiple comparison technique

Since $F(95\%)$ is the F-value corresponding to $P=0.05$ and an F-value more extreme will give a lower P value, the value $p < 0.05$ in Table (III) indicates that the mean TCO distributions over different longitudinal bands have a significant difference. This means that we obtained enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis. We have carried out a multiple comparison technique to investigate the difference among TCO measurements at different longitude bands as shown in Table (IV).

TABLE III: Standard Analysis of Variance Table for longitudinal bands (C_{lon}) (Eqn (2), $k=15$, $N=2890 \times 15$). Results demonstrate mean difference among the longitudinal bands

Source of Variation	Sum square	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	P
Between bands (Groups)	13867	14	990.3	67.06	< 0.001
Within bands (Error)	599662	40600	14.77		
Total	613529	40614			

TABLE IV: Longitudinal statistical variations of TCO measurements

Lon($^{\circ}$)	Lon($^{\circ}$)	Lower Limits	Upper Limits	$\mu_1 - \mu_2$	p-value
42.5	47.5	1.733	1.85	1.967	0.150
42.5	46.5	-0.901	0.22	1.338	1.000
42.5	45.5	-0.554	0.57	1.687	0.930
42.5	44.5	-1.219	-0.10	1.020	1.000
42.5	43.5	-1.35	-0.23	0.890	1.000
42.5	41.5	-1.537	-0.42	0.703	0.996
42.5	40.5	-0.356	0.36	1.073	0.895
39.5	38.5	-0.782	0.34	1.458	0.990
39.5	37.5	-0.200	0.92	2.04	0.255
39.5	36.5	-2.021	-0.90	0.219	0.287
39.5	35.5	-0.510	0.61	1.73	0.880
39.5	34.5	-1.744	0.62	0.496	0.859
39.5	33.5	-1.159	0.04	1.081	1.000

We can see from Table (IV) that the study area can be divided into two sub-regions based on the characteristics of TCO measurements as Western cluster covering the regions from $33.5^{\circ}E$ to $39.5^{\circ}E$ and Eastern cluster covering the region $40.5^{\circ}E$ to $47.5^{\circ}E$. A similar procedure follows for the latitudinal clustering as discussed below.

2. Latitudinal Clustering

Following the null hypothesis defined in the previous subsection but for latitudinal bands, we have carried out a similar investigation in order to cluster TCO measurements at different latitude bands.

Similar to the longitudinal clustering the value $p \leq 0.05$ in Table (V) shows that the average TCO measurements along different latitudinal bands differ significantly and this means that our null hypothesis is rejected. In Table (V) again, the total degree of freedom is 32557 due to the missing data values in C_{lat} (Eqn. 1) that can't be replaced with linear interpolation. We have carried out multiple comparison technique to study the level of statistical difference among TCO measurements over different latitudinal bands as shown in Table (VI).

Table (VI) depicts results of the multiple comparisons anal-

TABLE V: Standard Analysis of Variance Table for latitudinal bands (C_{lat}) (Eqn (1), $k=12$, $N=2890 \times 12$). Results demonstrate mean difference among the latitudinal bands

Source of Variation	Sum square	Degrees of Freedom	Mean Squares	F	P
Between bands (Groups)	5886.1	11	535.1	33.26	0.00001
Within bands (Error)	523670	32546	16.09		
Total	529556	32557			

TABLE VI: Latitudinal statistical variations of TCO measurements

Lat($^{\circ}$)	Lower Lat($^{\circ}$)	Lower Limits	$\mu_1 - \mu_2$	Upper Limits	p-value
13.5	14.5	0.4394	0.50	0.5526	0.9606
13.5	12.5	-0.0831	1.06	2.2057	0.0997
13.5	11.5	-1.7109	-0.57	0.5772	0.9025
13.5	10.5	-1.9826	-0.84	0.3055	0.4090
13.5	9.5	-2.1184	-0.97	0.1690	0.1862
6.5	8.5	-1.9065	-0.76	0.3810	0.5647
6.5	7.5	-1.4069	-0.26	0.8805	0.9998
6.5	5.5	-2.0219	-0.88	0.2658	0.3342
6.5	4.5	-2.0874	-0.94	0.2007	0.2286
6.5	3.5	-0.21	0.86	1.9300	0.0171

ysis. The comparisons clearly show that the study area can be divided into two sub-regions based on the statistical difference of the TCO measurements over different latitude as Southern region covering 4.5° to $8.5^{\circ}N$ and Northern region that covers 9.5° to $14.5^{\circ}N$. Here, the sample mean TCO value of $3.5^{\circ}N$ has a significant difference value from its nearest values (eg. for $6.5^{\circ}N - 3.5^{\circ}N$; the p-value is $p < 0.05$), which means they are not grouped in the same cluster. On the other hand, Table I (for $14.5^{\circ}N - 3.5^{\circ}N$ the value of $R^2 < 0.8$) indicates that the sample mean value at $3.5^{\circ}N$ cannot be expressed by the northernmost values. Hence, based on this analysis the band $3.5^{\circ}N$ was supposed to be a separate additional cluster, however, as indicated in Figure 1, the number of data points at 3.5° are only two, and both are at the boundary which means these are too small in number to be considered as a separate visible cluster as we are considering Ethiopia only in the map. Of course, this may indicate that if we were considering a region larger than Ethiopia we would have at least one more cluster that include $3.5^{\circ}N$ band.

3. Multiple Clustering

The discussions in the previous subsections on latitudinal and longitudinal clusters reveals the existence of two clusters for each latitudinal and longitudinal bands as Northern and Southern clusters for latitudinal bands, and Eastern and western clusters for longitudinal bands. It is useful to study

if a given cluster itself can be represented by another cluster as the classifications above have been done by considering one dimension and that is through the latitudinal or longitudinal bands separately. Classification through two-dimensional space allows proper mapping of TCO for practical application. We consider NW, NE, SW and SE regions for multiple clustering. Classification of clusters can be studied by means of multiple clustering methods following the approach by³³. The statistical parameters obtained by multiple clustering analysis of the clusters are presented in Table (VII).

TABLE VII: Statistical parameters obtained by multiple clustering.

Groups	Groups	Lower Limits	$\mu_1 - \mu_2$	Upper Limits	p-value
NW	NE	2.3599	3.2441	4.1243	0.0001
NW	SW	5.6625	6.5446	7.4267	0.0002
NW	SE	6.1906	7.0728	9.9549	0.001
NE	SW	2.4203	3.3025	4.1847	0.0004
NE	SE	2.9485	3.8307	4.7129	0.001
SW	SE	-0.3539	0.5282	1.4103	0.4145

In Table (VII) the lower p-values ($p < 0.05$) indicate that the mean TCO distributions over different sub-regions have a significant difference. However, the p-value in the last column ($P > 0.05$) demonstrates that there is no significant difference between the mean of South-Western and South-Eastern clusters. This means that we found that there is only three clusters of the mean TCO distributions over Ethiopia. These are North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern clusters as can be seen in Figure (3). The result is confirmed by Calinski-Harabasz criterion for Optimal number of clusters as indicated in Figure (2)

FIG. 2: Optimal number of clusters

The larger the VRCK ratio, the better the data partition. To determine the optimal number of clusters, maximize VRCK with respect to k ³⁴. The optimal number of clusters corresponds to the solution with the highest Calinski-Harabasz index value. As indicated in Figure 2, the Calinski-Harabasz criterion values were tested for each number of clusters. The result shows that the highest value of Calinski-Harabasz

indicates that the optimum number of clusters is three. We note we applied the internal cluster validation method to measure the quality of the cluster structure because there is no ground data. Therefore, it is a reliable model.

FIG. 3: Spatial distribution of Mean TCO.

Figure (3) shows high mean TCO concentration over the Northern part of Ethiopia and low concentration over the southern part of Ethiopia. This overall local increasing TCO variation result along latitude is inline with the global spatial TCO variation study³⁵. Moreover, we see that the overall three clusters of mean TCO over Ethiopia obtained through the proposed method are similar with the overall mean Rainfall distribution over Ethiopia^{36,37}. From Figure (3), it also seems that the mean TCO distributions looks inversely proportional with the surface temperature distributions over Ethiopia. However, the relation between TCO distributions with meteorological variables over the region might need a thorough investigation with state-of-the-art methods like Graeco-Latin square and we leave this for a subsequent study.

C. TCO Concentration over Seasons

We have studied the spatial TCO concentration over the study area by considering the overall temporal mean of every data point for all four seasons of Ethiopia including winter (DJF), spring (MAM), autumn (SON) and summer (JJA).

Figure (4) shows the spatial distribution of TCO over Ethiopia for each season. We can see that a relative maximum TCO concentration has been observed during the Summer (JJA) and a minimum concentration during the Winter (DJF) season. High-latitude regions have a relative maximum TCO while low-latitude ones experienced minimum values.

The variability of TCO concentration over the study area is assessed by calculating the coefficient of variation as the ratio

FIG. 4: Seasonal distribution of mean TCO over Ethiopia from 2012-2019, note that there is a scale difference in the seasonal panels. a: Winter(DJF), b: Spring(MAM), c: Summer(JJA), and d= Autumn(SON).

of the standard deviation to the mean for each data point as shown in Figure (5) using the overall mean TCO value.

FIG. 5: Spatial pattern of coefficient of variation (CV)

Figure (5) shows the variability of TCO concentration during the study period and it is found to be between 4.75% and 5.7%. One can see a relatively lower variations the South-Eastern part of Ethiopia. The mean TCO concentration in the Northern and Central parts of Ethiopia is relatively higher than the concentration in most of the Southern parts of Ethiopia.

D. Temporal TCO Distribution

In order to analyze the temporal characteristics of TCO over the three clusters, we assess the mean, standard deviation, coefficient of variation and extreme values of TCO is given in Table (VIII).

Table (VIII) shows that the mean TCO concentration was 264.29DU, 261.0DU and 258.73DU over North-Western, North-Eastern, Southern clusters respectively. Moreover, the overall population mean TCO of Ethiopia was found to be $261.35 \pm 2.38DU$. Table (VIII) and the raw data showed that the TCO concentration has a maximum value of 301DU

TABLE VIII: Mean, Standard Deviation and Coefficient of variation over all sub-regions

Region	Mean			Minimum TCO(DU)	Maximum TCO(DU)
	TCO(DU)	std	CV%		
NW	264.29	13.6	5.15	217	301
NE	261.0	13.73	5.26	217	298
SO	258.73	11.28	4.36	216	299
ETH	261.35	12.62	1.07	216	301

during summer on August 18, 2013 and a minimum value of 216DU during winter on January 03, 2013 over the study period. The concentration of TCO clearly shows increasing values with latitudinal changes from South to North which is consistent with the previous studies carried out in other regions^{1,38,39}.

1. Timeseries Analysis

We investigated the seasonal nature and trend of ozone distributions through timeseries analysis. This is carried out by decomposing the daily timeseries data into trends, seasonal variations, and residual components for each cluster regions independently. The time-series data can be modeled as an additive form due to its similar seasonal effect in each year⁴⁰. The trend of the TCO variations cannot be identified easily because of the seasonal cyclic variations²⁵. In this study we have detected the period of seasonal pattern by using two different techniques. Visual inspection of timeseries plot as indicated on Figure 6 can be considered as one option.

FIG. 6: Monthly Mean TCO over clusters

From the sequences of timeseries data plots in Figure 6, the concentration over all of the sub-regions was highest during June, July, and August. It also shows the concentration decreases until December and then rises continuously to July, and hence the annual cyclic behavior is observed. On the other hand, the seasonality of TCO is estimated from the best fit of daily TCO timeseries^(25,26). We also estimated the cyclic variability of TCO by best fitting of measured data through Fourier series model given by equation 9. In order to identify the dominant frequencies of a timeseries, we used a power spectrum Fast Fourier Transform on our measured data which is given in terms of frequency instead of period as indicated in

Figure. 7.

FIG. 7: spectral periodogram a)NWC, b) NEC & c) SOC of Ethiopia

The spectral periodogram plot shows that there is a single Fourier power peak with the corresponding frequency $f = 0.002768\text{Hz}$ for all clusters. The inverse of this frequency, which is period of the annual cyclic behavior, is 365.25 days. This result is in line with the previous studies by^{16,25,26,41}.

TABLE IX: Tests of goodness of fit for seasonal components

Cluster		Fourier terms(n)	
		n = 1	n = 2
NW	R^2	0.7865	0.8090
	RMSE	6.2338	5.9002
NE	R^2	0.7959	0.8146
	RMSE	6.1597	5.8741
SO	R^2	0.6835	0.7007
	RMSE	6.3229	6.1536

Table IX shows that for a Fourier term $n = 1$: the coefficients of determination (R^2) are 0.7865, 0.7959, and 0.6835 for North-Western, North-Eastern, and Southern clusters respectively. In North-Western and North-Eastern clusters the coefficient of determination (R^2) is higher than 0.7 and it is considered as a good seasonal fit³². However, the coefficient of determination (R^2) for the Southern cluster was lower than 0.7 and its coefficient of determination (R^2) for $n=2$ is higher than 0.70. In this case, we used $n=1$ for North-Western & North-Eastern clusters while $n=2$ for the Southern cluster. It shows that we have a Fourier transform term of $n = 1$ for

North-Western & North-Eastern clusters while $n = 2$ for the Southern cluster. The estimated parameters for seasonal components of each cluster are presented in Table X below.

TABLE X: Parameter Estimation for seasonal components

Cluster	Estimates			
	α_1	β_1	α_2	β_2
NW	-16.85	3.843		
NE	-16.56	3.852		
SO	-13.14	1.616	-1.344	1.512

Now, the coefficients of the fitting functions indicated in Table X have a coefficient of determination (R^2) of 0.7865, 0.7959, and 0.7007 for North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern clusters respectively.

The equations for the seasonality component becomes $S_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \cos(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25}) + \beta_1 \sin(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25})$ for North-Western & North-Eastern clusters and

$$S_t = \alpha_0 + \alpha_1 \cos(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25}) + \beta_1 \sin(\frac{2\pi t}{365.25}) + \alpha_2 \cos(\frac{4\pi t}{365.25}) + \beta_2 \sin(\frac{4\pi t}{365.25}), \text{ for Southern cluster.}$$

Moreover, the seasonal component is the best fit of measured data as indicated in Figure (8).

FIG. 8: the seasonal components over a) North-Western, b) North-Eastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

In order to assess the long term monotonic trend, first we have defined a 5% threshold with null hypothesis as there is no monotonic trend and we have applied non-parametric Mann-Kendall trend test.

TABLE XI: Mann-Kendall trend test result over the three clusters

	Clusters		
	NWC	NEC	SOC
N	2890	2890	2890
S-val	-422952	-401190	-230736
Z-stat	-8.1649	-7.7448	-4.4543
P-val	< 0.0001	< 0.0001	< 0.0001

The P-value of < 0.05 in Table (XI) indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis H_0 : and it reveals the existence of

monotonic trend over all the three clusters. The long term increasing or decreasing pattern of TCO timeseries have been modeled using linear trend in Africa²⁹. In this study as well, we assumed a linear trend defined by equation (14). The deseasonalized TCO data and the corresponding linear fitted line is summarized as follows.

FIG. 9: Deseasonalized data with a fitted line over a) North-Western, b) North-Eastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

We obtained the linear trend equations corresponding to each cluster TCO timeseries as $y_{nw} = -0.0021x + 3.066$, $y_{ne} = -0.00201x + 3$, and $y_s = -0.0012x + 2.079$ for monthly ozone concentration over the North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern clusters of Ethiopia, respectively. We have given in Figure (9) deseasonalized timeseries plots together with the fitted trends for each cluster. In all the cases, the results show a decreasing trend with a depletion rate of 0.77 DU/yr, 0.73 DU/yr, and 0.43 DU/yr over North-Western, North-Eastern and Southern parts of Ethiopia respectively.

To strengthen the current study, as the serial correlated residual in Figure (9) show that runs of high and low values tend to persist for a few months, and to see the robustness of the trend even in the presence of serial correlation, we implement the Mann-Kendall test on the deseasonalized timeseries averaged into DJF-MAM-JJA-SON (3-month means for each year). We have given in Table XII Mann-Kendall trend test result for the deseasonalized three months mean timeseries for illustration purpose.

TABLE XII: The three months mean deseasonalized data Mann-Kendall trend test result for the three clusters

	Clusters		
	NWC	NEC	SOC
N	32	32	32
S-val	-142	-138	-82
Z-stat	-2.287	-2.221	-1.313
P-val	0.022	0.026	0.189

The P-value of < 0.05 in Table (XII) indicates the rejection of the null hypothesis and it reveals the existence of monotonic trend for NWC and NEC. Hence, the test result reveals again the existence of similar monotonic trend for Northwest

and Northeast clusters timeseries. However, for the southern cluster the Mann-Kendall test shows no significant trend which might be due the structural noise is a bit higher than the corresponding trend in this cluster which shows the impact of significant serial correlation on trend estimates. For the model predictive performance evaluation, we use two sets of performance metrics, namely residual diagnostics and autocorrelation tests. The objective is to determine whether the residuals of the models resemble white noise or not. Figures 10,11 and 12 show different residual plots, the top panels show the residuals plot of the temporally correlated noises ε_t with non constant variances in the model, the middle panels show that the plot of residuals v_t from which the correlation is removed in the block AR model. The bottom panels show the plot of the standardized residuals $v_t/\hat{\sigma}_t$, using the fitted standard deviation, which resembles gaussian noise.

FIG. 10: Residual plots over NWC a) Correlated Noises with non constant Variance b) Correlation Removed Residual & c) standardized residuals

FIG. 11: Residual plots over NEC a) Correlated Noises with non constant Variance b) Correlation Removed Residual & c) standardized residuals

The autocorrelation plot of the standardized residuals $v_t/\hat{\sigma}_t$ in Figure 13, also suggests that there is no significant serial correlation left in the residuals.

The estimated parameters for residual components of each of the three clusters are presented in Table XIII. In Figure (14), we give TCO plot with two-sigma model output confidence interval to indicate the model's accuracy. This helped us

FIG. 12: Residual plots over SOC a) Correlated Noises with non constant Variance b) Correlation Removed Residual & c) standardized residuals

FIG. 13: ACF plot over a) North-Western, b) North-Eastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

TABLE XIII: Parameter Estimation for Residual components

Cluster	Estimates		
	ϕ_1	ϕ_2	ϕ_1
NWC	0.8212	-0.0503	0.0933
NEC	0.8591	-0.0558	-0.0922
SOC	0.9375	-0.1205	0.1351

quantify the uncertainty of the sample estimates for the entire TCO time series. As the range is narrow, the margin of error is small and it is a range of plausible values which shows the model's output is reasonably good. We also have checked the overall model performance by computing the R^2 between the model output and the time series data. We obtained R^2 values of 0.85, 0.86, 0.79 for NWC, NEC and SOC respectively and

FIG. 14: The Confidence interval of the model a) Northwestern, b) Northeastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

the result indicates the overall goodness of fit of the model is reasonably good. In order to evaluate the reliability of these models in describing the data, we also investigate the residuals of the models if they resemble white noise.

FIG. 15: QQ plot for Remaining Components a) Northwestern, b) Northeastern & c) Southern clusters of Ethiopia

The normal probability quantile-quantile plot of the standardized residual given in Figure (15) shows that the residuals can be regarded as Gaussian noise without any signs of large outliers and hence the proposed time series model is reliable for this set of data. In general, based on this study and the results of other researchers over Kenya, West Africa, and Pakistan^{1,42,15,29}, the source of seasonal variability of ozone distribution over Ethiopia may be mainly due to ozone transport and chemistry. However, in order to reach a more strong conclusion, the impact of Quasi-Biennial Oscillation (QBO) and Solar UV radiation on the variability of ozone over Ethiopia should be studied in detail.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have studied the spatiotemporal distribution of total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia using OMPS- NM satellite daily data from 108 data points over Ethiopia for the period of 2012-2019. The study has shown that the maximum total column ozone concentration occurred during

the summer seasons, while the minimum measurements were recorded during the winter seasons in North-Western and Central Ethiopia. The annual mean total column ozone concentration during the study period is found to be (261.35 ± 2.38) DU. The maximum total column ozone of 301 DU was observed on 18 August 2013 while the minimum of 216 DU was measured on January 03, 2013.

We have also showed through spatial data clustering study that the spatial distribution of the total column ozone concentration over Ethiopia can be classified into three major representative clusters: Southern Cluster ($4.5^{\circ}N$ to $8.5^{\circ}N$ & $33.5^{\circ}E$ – $47.5^{\circ}E$), North-Eastern Cluster ($9.5^{\circ}N$ to $14.5^{\circ}N$ & $41.5^{\circ}E$ to $47.5^{\circ}E$) and North-Western Cluster ($9.5^{\circ}N$ to $14.5^{\circ}N$ & $33.5^{\circ}E$ to $40.5^{\circ}E$). Our TCO timeseries analysis has shown a decreasing linear trend in TCO with a depletion rate of 0.77 DU/yr, 0.73 DU/yr, and 0.43 DU/yr over North-Western, North-Eastern & Southern clusters of Ethiopia respectively. We also found a single power peak with the frequency of $f = 0.002768 Hz$ with annual cyclic behavior of $\frac{1}{f} \approx 365.25$ days from spectral periodogram for the three clusters.

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DECLARATIONS

Availability of data and material

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in National Oceanic & Atmospheric Administration, at <https://www.esrl.noaa.gov/gmd/grad/neubrew/SatO3DataTimeSeries.jsp>⁴³

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interest.

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REFERENCES

- ¹L. Rafiq, S. Tajbar, and S. Manzoor, "Long term temporal trends and spatial distribution of total ozone over pakistan," *The Egyptian Journal of Remote Sensing and Space Science* **20**, 295–301 (2017).

- ²H. Kambezidis, E. Katevatis, M. Petrakis, S. Lykoudis, and D. Asimakopoulos, "Estimation of the linke and unsworth-monteith turbidity factors in the visible spectrum: application for athens, greece," *Solar Energy* **62**, 39–50 (1998).
- ³M. Rex, R. Salawitch, P. von der Gathen, N. Harris, M. Chipperfield, and B. Naujokat, "Arctic ozone loss and climate change," *Geophysical Research Letters* **31** (2004).
- ⁴D. Fahey, P. A. Newman, J. A. Pyle, B. Safari, M. P. Chipperfield, D. Karoly, D. E. Kinnison, M. Ko, M. Santee, and S. J. Doherty, "Scientific assessment of ozone depletion: 2018, global ozone research and monitoring project-report no. 58," (2018).
- ⁵P. Huck, S. Tilmes, G. Bodeker, W. Randel, A. McDonald, and H. Nakajima, "An improved measure of ozone depletion in the antarctic stratosphere," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* **112** (2007).
- ⁶A. Pazmiño, S. Godin-Beekmann, A. Hauchecorne, C. Claud, S. Khaykin, F. Goutail, E. Wolfgram, J. Salvador, and E. Quel, "Multiple symptoms of total ozone recovery inside the antarctic vortex during austral spring," *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **18**, 7557–7572 (2018).
- ⁷M. Saraiya, K. Glanz, P. A. Briss, P. Nichols, C. White, D. Das, S. J. Smith, B. Tannor, A. B. Hutchinson, K. M. Wilson, *et al.*, "Interventions to prevent skin cancer by reducing exposure to ultraviolet radiation: a systematic review," *American journal of preventive medicine* **27**, 422–466 (2004).
- ⁸F. Anwar, F. N. Chaudhry, S. Nazeer, N. Zaman, and S. Azam, "Causes of Ozone Layer Depletion and Its Effects on Human: Review," *Atmospheric and Climate Sciences* **06**, 129–134 (2016).
- ⁹T. Sivasakthivel and K. Reddy, "Ozone layer depletion and its effects: a review," *International Journal of Environmental Science and Development* **2**, 30–37 (2011).
- ¹⁰M. Chipperfield, "A three-dimensional model study of long-term mid-high latitude lower stratosphere ozone changes," *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **3**, 1253–1265 (2003).
- ¹¹X. Liu, P. Bhartia, K. Chance, R. Spurr, and T. Kurosu, "Ozone profile retrievals from the ozone monitoring instrument," *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **10**, 2521–2537 (2010).
- ¹²P. J. Aucamp, L. O. Björn, and R. Lucas, "Questions and answers about the environmental effects of ozone depletion and its interactions with climate change: 2010 assessment," *Photochemical & Photobiological Sciences* **10**, 301–316 (2011).
- ¹³J. Oggunniyi and V. Sivakumar, "Ozone climatology and its variability from ground based and satellite observations over irene, south africa (25.5 ° s; 28.1 ° e)-part 2: Total column ozone variations," *Atmosfera* **31**, 11–24 (2018).
- ¹⁴N. R. Harris, E. Kyrö, J. Staehelin, D. Brunner, S.-B. Andersen, S. Godin-Beekmann, S. Dhomse, P. Hadjinicolaou, G. Hansen, I. Isaksen, *et al.*, "Ozone trends at northern mid-and high latitudes—a european perspective," in *Annales Geophysicae*, Vol. 26 (Copernicus Publications Göttingen, Germany, 2008) pp. 1207–1220.
- ¹⁵V. Madhu *et al.*, "Madden julian oscillations in total column ozone, air temperature and surface pressure measured over cochin during summer monsoon 2015," *Open Journal of Marine Science* **6**, 270 (2016).
- ¹⁶L. Chen, B. Yu, Z. Chen, B. Li, and J. Wu, "Investigating the temporal and spatial variability of total ozone column in the yangtze river delta using satellite data: 1978–2013," *Remote Sensing* **6**, 12527–12543 (2014).
- ¹⁷A. Bais, D. Lubin, A. Arola, G. Bernhard, M. Blumthaler, N. Chubarova, C. Erlick, H. Gies, N. Krotkov, K. Lantz, *et al.*, "Surface ultraviolet radiation: past, present, and future," *Scientific assessment of ozone depletion 7*, 2007 (2006).
- ¹⁸M. G. Dittman, E. Ramberg, M. Chrisp, J. V. Rodriguez, A. L. Sparks, N. H. Zaun, P. Hendershot, T. Dixon, R. H. Philbrick, and D. Wasinger, "Nadir ultraviolet imaging spectrometer for the npoess ozone mapping and profiler suite (omps)," in *Earth Observing Systems VII*, Vol. 4814 (International Society for Optics and Photonics, 2002) pp. 111–119.
- ¹⁹R. McPeters, S. Frith, N. Kramarova, J. Ziemke, and G. Labow, "Trend quality ozone from npp omps: the version 2 processing," *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques* **12**, 977–985 (2019).
- ²⁰S. Takele Kenea, G. Mengistu Tsidu, T. Blumenstock, F. Hase, T. Von Clarmann, and G. Stiller, "Retrieval and satellite intercomparison of o 3 measurements from ground-based ftir spectrometer at equatorial station: Addis ababa, ethiopia," *Atmospheric Measurement Techniques* **6** (2013).
- ²¹Z. Chen, B. Yu, Y. Huang, Y. Hu, H. Lin, and J. Wu, "Validation of total ozone column derived from omps using ground-based spectroradiometer measurements," *Remote sensing letters* **4**, 937–945 (2013).
- ²²J. Berbert, J. Brown, T. Felsentreger, D. Harris, T. Johnson, M. Khan, F. Lerch, J. Marsh, J. Murphy, B. Putney, *et al.*, "National aeronautics and space administration/goddard space flight center," *NASA Special Publication* **365**, 293 (1977).
- ²³M. H. Kutner, C. J. Nachtsheim, J. Neter, W. Li, *et al.*, *Applied linear statistical models*, Vol. 5 (McGraw-Hill Irwin New York, 2005).
- ²⁴M. Hamada and J. Wu, *Experiments: planning, analysis, and parameter design optimization* (Wiley New York, 2000).
- ²⁵M. Antón, D. Bortoli, M. J. Costa, P. S. Kulkarni, A. F. Domingues, D. Barriopedro, A. Serrano, and A. M. Silva, "Remote Sensing of Environment Temporal and spatial variabilities of total ozone column over Portugal," *Remote Sensing of Environment* **115**, 855–863 (2011).
- ²⁶V. Fioletov, G. Labow, R. Evans, E. Hare, U. Köhler, C. McElroy, K. Miyagawa, A. Redondas, V. Savastouk, A. Shalamyansky, *et al.*, "Performance of the ground-based total ozone network assessed using satellite data," *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* **113** (2008).
- ²⁷A. W. Schmalwieser, G. Schaubberger, and M. Janouch, "Temporal and spatial variability of total ozone content over central europe: analysis in respect to the biological effect on plants," *Agricultural and forest meteorology* **120**, 9–26 (2003).
- ²⁸C. Libiseller, A. Grimvall, J. Waldén, and H. Saari, "Meteorological normalisation and non-parametric smoothing for quality assessment and trend analysis of tropospheric ozone data," *Environmental monitoring and assessment* **100**, 33–52 (2005).
- ²⁹A. Oluleye and E. C. Okogbue, "Analysis of temporal and spatial variability of total column ozone over west africa using daily toms measurements," *Atmospheric Pollution Research* **4**, 387–397 (2013).
- ³⁰B. E. Hansen, "Time series analysis james d. hamilton princeton university press, 1994," *Econometric Theory* **11**, 625–630 (1995).
- ³¹E. Kyrölä, M. Laine, V. Sofieva, J. Tamminen, S.-M. Päiväranta, S. Tukiainen, J. Zawodny, and L. Thomason, "Combined sage ii-gomos ozone profile data set for 1984–2011 and trend analysis of the vertical distribution of ozone," *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **13**, 10645–10658 (2013).
- ³²H. Akoglu, "User's guide to correlation coefficients," *Turkish Journal of Emergency Medicine* **18**, 91–93 (2018).
- ³³C. Boulis and M. Ostendorf, "Combining multiple clustering systems," in *European Conference on Principles of Data Mining and Knowledge Discovery* (Springer, 2004) pp. 63–74.
- ³⁴K. Firuzi, M. Vakilian, V. Darabad, B. Phung, and T. Blackburn, "A novel method for differentiating and clustering multiple partial discharge sources using s transform and bag of words feature," *IEEE Transactions on Dielectrics and Electrical Insulation* **24**, 3694–3702 (2017).
- ³⁵M. L. Stein, "Spatial variation of total column ozone on a global scale," *The Annals of Applied Statistics* **1**, 191–210 (2007).
- ³⁶B. Berhanu, Y. Seleshi, S. S. Demisse, and A. M. Melesse, "Bias correction and characterization of climate forecast system re-analysis daily precipitation in ethiopia using fuzzy overlay," *Meteorological Applications* **23**, 230–243 (2016).
- ³⁷N. Wagesho, N. K. Goel, and M. K. Jain, "Temporal and spatial variability of annual and seasonal rainfall over ethiopia," *Hydrological Sciences Journal* **58**, 354–373 (2013).
- ³⁸A. J. Krueger, "The global distribution of total ozone: Toms satellite measurements," *Planetary and Space Science* **37**, 1555–1565 (1989).
- ³⁹J. London, "The observed distribution of atmospheric ozone and its variations," IN: *Ozone in the free atmosphere*. New York, Van Nostrand Reinhold Co., 1985, p. 11–80. , 11–80 (1985).
- ⁴⁰Y. Dodge and D. Commenges, *The Oxford dictionary of statistical terms* (Oxford University Press on Demand, 2006).
- ⁴¹C. Vigouroux, T. Blumenstock, M. Coffey, Q. Errera, O. García, N. B. Jones, J. W. Hannigan, F. Hase, B. Liley, E. Mahieu, J. Mellqvist, J. Notholt, M. Palm, G. Persson, M. Schneider, C. Servais, D. Smale, L. Thölix, and M. De Mazière, "Trends of ozone total columns and vertical distribution from ftir observations at eight ndacc stations around the globe," *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* **15**, 2915–2933 (2015).
- ⁴²C. M. M. Songa, *Modeling the Solar Forcing of the Total Column Ozone Variation in Selected Cities in Kenya*, Ph.D. thesis, COPAS, JKUAT (2017).
- ⁴³N. O. . A. Administration, "Omi/omps ozone time series data," (2019).